

ARCHITECTURE AS INTERACTION: A CONVERSATION WITH THEODORE SPYROPOULOS

KHÖREIN: In your work with students at the Design Research Lab at the AA School, architecture seems to be approached less through pre-defined methods or rules and more through conditions in which control is partially suspended. Would you describe your pedagogy as consciously non-didactic, and what kind of knowledge emerges when learning cannot be fully articulated in advance?

THEODORE SPYROPOULOS: Control from this point of view is an illusion and, one could say, it limits and prescribes the nature of enquiry. Thomas Kuhn in *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* spoke to this when he critically suggested that within the domain of research the questions that we ask inform the answers that we find. This is both obvious and profound when explored within science and the pursuit of knowledge. For me the issues around design research remain an active search through thematic subjects which by necessity need to be approached in an open and non-didactic manner. Part of my role as the Director now for over two decades is to foster a culture that is curious and experimental as a means to challenge the orthodoxies of response. To explore ideas through what the subjects demand rather than a methodology that projects a style or predefined solution space. This means moving beyond a prescriptive response into an active form of learning that is engaged with the capacity to work collectively on the complexities that the research necessitates. This is not experimentation for the sake of experimentation but the means to examine critical questions that challenge the means we work and apply this research. This is for all who participate in this experiment we call the DRL. A culture where staff and students are exploring complex ideas as a collective, a team. No hierarchies but leveraging our experiences and work in a way that assists us to work through a great deal of challenges: conceptual, social, and technical together. Where the

outputs of research are examined from multiple perspectives and where risk is encouraged to push the boundaries.

Knowledge from this perspective is constructed through active engagement that approaches subjects as spaces of enquiry, while attempting to build a literacy that is shared and examined in, for example, simulation environments, observational experiments, historical case studies, and within many bodies of knowledge that are usually outside of the discipline of architecture. This manner of working is in constant dialogue with the material and each other and I believe gives agency to our students and staff bringing a vitality to the collective search. It is a mutually supportive environment that is working with a belief that design can offer people more. Creating a meaningful engagement that challenges all forms of conceptualisation.

KH: Many projects developed under your mentorship generate form through distributed interactions rather than individual intention. How do you understand authorship under these conditions, and what changes when the architect is no longer the primary source of form?

TS: This approach explores both human and non-human forms of interaction. In attempting to humanise technologies and respond to some of today's challenges, the work moves beyond the authoring of buildings to explore architecture as infrastructure, phenomenon as technology, material systems as self-aware and self-assembled systems, and urbanism as adaptive ecologies. My approach challenges individual authorship by recognising that some questions require forms of inquiry that can only be addressed collectively, due to the scale or complexity of the problem. Within this process, the role of the individual within the team shifts as the research develops. It is a co-authorship model that is diverse in its approach and plural in its inputs, both within the team and in response to the technologies or subjects being explored.

Historically, the role of the architect has always involved interfacing with others and sustaining an active dialogue in the realisation of ideas. Yet the privileging of individual authorship remains an orthodoxy within educational structures and in how the architect is projected in society. In the introduction to my PhD titled *Constructing Participatory Environments: A Behavioural Model for Design*, I attempted to address this idea by describing architecture as an ecology of interacting systems. It looked to people like Gordon Pask that sought to think of interaction models

through what he spoke about as Conversation Theory. This could be seen in the development of projects that embraced this open framework in a project like the Fun Palace with Cedric Price and Joan Littlewood as an example.¹

KH: Having worked in proximity to figures such as Peter Eisenman and Patrik Schumacher, both of whom are associated with strong and highly articulated theoretical positions, how did these experiences influence your own approach, particularly your move toward open-ended, experimental and system-based forms of practice?

TS: I was fortunate early in my career to be exposed to environments that never created an artificial divide between theory and practice. This resonated with me, and in particular in Peter's office, where this was clearly manifested within architecture. In preparation for his lectures for his classes at Yale or Princeton, he would share and work through these theories and speculations with us during our lunchtime in the office. I enjoyed this engagement intellectually and found it very important for me in engaging with and contributing to the work at the time in the office. During this period, aside from working on competitions with him, we had projects such as the City of Culture in Galicia, Spain, the Berlin Memorial, and the Arizona football stadium being worked on. As the office was small and the work complex, it was more the setup of a European football team, where we all contributed in the ways the projects necessitated. It was through Peter and this period in the office that I understood what a project in architecture could be. It was a continued education for me as I joined post my studies at the Architectural Association.

¹ "This thesis proposes the design of cybernetic frameworks that attempt to explore architecture as ecology of interacting systems that move beyond the fixed and finite tendencies of the past towards spatial environments that are adaptive, emotive and behavioural. Environments within this framework are attempts to construct interaction scenarios that enable agency, curiosity and play, forging intimate exchanges that are participatory and evolving over time. Interaction understood as the evolving relationships between things allows a generative and time-based framework to explore space as a model of interfacing that shifts the tendencies of passive occupancy towards an active ecology of interacting agents. The work argued here moves away from known models that reinforce habitual responses within architecture, towards an understanding of adaptive systems that are active agents for communication and exploration. Architecture within the context of this thesis is explored as a medium for spatial interfacing. Design is thus considered as durational, real-time and anticipatory exploring human human, human machine, and machine machine communication. The challenge posed is how designers can construct environments that are shared, enable curiosity, evolve and allow for complex interactions to arise through human and non-human agency."

In the work of Patrik and Zaha, this was different. In Zaha, you had an intuitive force that had a vision and sensibility that was formally expressive and elegantly delivered through various media. Patrik theorised this and evolved it through models of organisation, translating this vision to the scale that the work was radically evolving towards. Their collaboration shaped a practice that created a framework to allow an atelier-like office to scale from 5 to 500 and maintain a sensibility. Patrik's theoretical position, which he articulated in *Autopoiesis of Architecture* (2010) and through the term of Parametricism that he coined in 2008 at the Venice Architecture Biennale, was always in direct dialogue with the DRL and his work within the lab. In particular, this emerged when we set up a research agenda in 2005 with colleagues titled Parametric Urbanism. Here, Patrik incubated many of the emerging aspects of his design theory in dialogue with the work at the office on masterplans, such as One North in Singapore (2001), which were a sign of things to come.

My theories drew from art movements of the 1970s New York art scene, quantum physics, computation, adaptive systems, and second-order cybernetics. That manifested in the work that I have pursued through Minimaforms, my two decades of directing the DRL, publications like *Adaptive Ecologies*, and my PhD, where I wrote on relationality and behaviour and approaches towards design that folded uncertainty and latency as important factors in the nature of how and what we worked on.

In contrast to Patrik's parametric approach, I developed a theoretical framework for a model of urbanism that was not guided by top-down formalism, but by generative and behavioural systems that were emergent and relational. This was a position from my side that was against master planning and sought examining poly-scalar relationships that foregrounded computational frameworks that allow for change. Through an active dialogue, this project evolved into a discourse that was applied in proposals and created meaningful project discussions that have remained spirited within the DRL. Though there are at times radically different points of view between our work within the DRL, our collaboration has offered a dynamic and multifaceted point of view that is plural. Nurturing an environment where differences in the development of research are welcomed and important. This for me affords a context to prototype ideas and engage with collaborators who offer a deep engagement with the project of architecture. This within a collaborative design research environment the likes of the DRL allow an explorative model for design.

In my work, if the issues could be explored spatially, then I believed they were architectural and our knowledge could have an important contribution. I have allowed that understanding to lead me, and my efforts to be shaped through open experimentation. The shift from representational forms of communication to active prototyping, and from human to non-human engagement, allowed me to move intellectually and in the realisation of the work in a dynamic manner. Rather than applying a language, I allowed for languages to be born through active and collective research and experimentation.

KH: Collapse, deviation, and failure appear frequently in experimental work at the DRL, though not as mistakes in a conventional sense. Has error become a productive condition of architectural thinking, and how do you distinguish it from a genuine loss of disciplinary criteria?

TS: Failure here is not failure. Rather, it is an attempt to examine and construct an approach that moves beyond forms of representation toward the active prototyping of ideas. By constructing proofs of concept, the work enables more informed questions and allows the research to generate an active feedback loop. As Samuel Beckett expressed beautifully: “Ever tried. Ever failed. No matter. Try again. Fail again. Fail better.” I would argue that this does not represent a loss of disciplinary criteria, but rather a critical enquiry into the ways we explore design. It purposefully opens up habitual responses to questions, allowing us to engage with them in more meaningful ways.

KH: In your work, where architecture unfolds over time rather than stabilising into a fixed form, how does this affect the way space is remembered or internalised? Does temporality itself become an active agent, participating in the shaping of spatial experience rather than simply framing it?

TS: Our work is conceptually about formation rather than form. Form here is understood as a moment in time. This draws from our understandings in the sciences and has served to influence the name of our practice, *Minimaforms*. The name recognises that form is arrested in time, and that this moment of understanding is the minima—when form comes into being.

With Stephen, my brother, we wanted to explore work that was emotive, behaviour-based, that gave agency and formed a collective memory.

In works from *Memory Cloud* to more recent projects such as *Of and In the World*, observers are active participants rather than passive observers. The approach is motivated by enabling agency and constructing frameworks that unfold over time.

KH: Your projects often unfold over time rather than arriving at a final state. How does this temporal openness affect how architectural work is evaluated, documented or remembered?

TS: In my work with *Minimaforms*, and with my students and staff at the DRL, there is a conceptual shift from the fixed and finite toward the dynamic and evolving. There is a deliberate questioning of the limits of representation, accompanied by a move toward the active prototyping of ideas.

The shift from form to formation was an early driver of the work, recognising our world as something that unfolds in time. It was an attempt to examine agency and to develop models that consider intelligence as something not unique to humans. This explores other forms of intelligence, ecologies, and environments as active participants in our architectural and artistic developments.

The work seeks to develop design systems that remain open frameworks for spatial interfacing, while recognising that many issues may remain latent or uncertain. This uncertainty as the only certainty which necessitates an approach to consider adaptive systems, systems of learning and behaviour. The aim from my perspective is to consider relationality as would be described in quantum physics as means to understand space time. To consider intelligence not as an attribute to a thing itself but a demonstration between things. This brings the world of quantum physics and second order cybernetics together for me.

KH: Your work engages many ideas historically associated with cybernetics—interaction, feedback, behaviour. Do you see this as a continuation of that lineage, or has contemporary machine learning shifted these questions into a fundamentally different terrain?

TS: The work of second-order cybernetics has been an important reference in developing systems and frameworks, particularly those exploring models of the brain and systems of learning. This includes cyberneticians such as Gordon Pask, Gregory Bateson, and W. Grey Walter. Pask is perhaps most well-known through his work in architecture with Cedric

Price, John and Julia Frazer, and MIT's Architecture Machine Group, as well as his exhibitions of cybernetic sculptures in seminal exhibitions such as *Cybernetic Serendipity* at the ICA in London.

What I find important in this work is that much of it was conceived as thought experiments, without direct access to the technologies that now make up our contemporary condition. From AI and machine learning to the concept of the black box, it was conceptually vast in scope and offered a means to examine complexity. Pask, in his paper "The Architectural Relevance of Cybernetics," spoke to the fact that, for him, architecture did not yet have a theory or means to deal with complexity. His interest in architecture was grounded in the belief that cybernetics could become that theory.

In our work, in particular that which explores interaction and systems design, we examine Pask's concept of conversation theory as a model to explore more participatory means of engaging the everyday. His work explored learning and novelty, while our work explores collective intelligence and emotive response. In a time where our AI systems are designing systems, we once again find ourselves in a condition of black box understandings—algorithms designing algorithms that offer solutions but no means to understand them within the knowledge structures we have been educated in.

This necessitates new forms of understanding and participation with these systems. So yes, it has evolved into something new, though that period was faced with similar engagements that were not disciplinary-specific, and I believe their questions are ever more important in understanding how we arrived here. My attempts are to demystify and humanise technology.

KH: In projects involving adaptive systems, you have explored installations that use machine learning to develop emotive forms of interaction, communicating through movement, sound, and other sensory cues. What would it mean to live with such systems architecturally, and how do they complicate distinctions between automation, autonomy, and affect?

TS: An example that illustrates this approach is Minimaforms' project *Petting Zoo*. The intention of this work is to respond to a robotic and automated future that many of my colleagues embrace as a dominant model of production. *Petting Zoo* explored the more complex question of how we might live with these systems. It marks a purposeful shift away from

the drivers of production, assembly, and fabrication toward emotive and behavioural forms of interfacing. The project is a speculative, life-like robotic environment that raises questions about how future environments might actively enable new forms of communication with the everyday. The artificially intelligent creatures are designed with the capacity to learn and explore behaviours through interaction with participants.

The installation exhibited life-like attributes through conversational forms of interaction, establishing communication with users that is both emotive and sensorial. Conceived as an immersive installation environment, social and synthetic systems of interaction allow the pets to engage with participants and evolve their behaviours over time. The pets stimulate participation through animate behaviours communicated through movement, sound, and illumination. These behaviours evolve through continued interaction, enabling each pet to develop distinct personalities. Interactions are stimulated through engagement with human users as well as with other pets within the population. Intimacy and curiosity act as enabling agents, externalising personal experience through direct visual, haptic, and aural forms of communication.

These experiments explore artificial intelligence as a means of prompting us to consider how we might co-evolve and inhabit future human-machine environments. Moving beyond robotics understood primarily as tools of production, *Petting Zoo* examines the emotive and behavioural dimensions of our engagement with these systems and with each other. Over time, and in response to habit, the pets can be understood to develop a form of “personality.” As the spatial orientation and environmental conditions of the installation generate diverse interaction scenarios for each pet, they gradually develop a unique capacity to exhibit varied behaviours. These personalities evolve through a process of systemic self-observation, opening new territories for exploring how we might design systems that evolve alongside us.

It speaks to the capacity of humans to see life like attributes in the synthetic systems. To humanise technologies and our empathy towards them when they are designed with features that engage us and stimulate curiosity.

KH: If, as Michael Polanyi argues, we know more than we can explicitly articulate, how should architecture relate to the opaque systems it increasingly relies on? Can the black box function as a meaningful architectural condition, rather than merely a technical limitation?

TS: I agree with the argument made by Polanyi. Quantum physics reminds us that how we see the world and how the world actually is can be very different. The “black box” therefore remains an important conceptual apparatus. From early cybernetic thinking, beginning with the Macy Conferences, to the present, it has served as a way of framing thought experiments that allow us to move both conceptually and technically in ways that are powerful because of their generative capacity.

Today this issue re-emerges in the need to transform the black box condition into a meaningful framework for engaging with our ever-evolving technological present. For instance, we now design processes that themselves design other processes, as seen in many developments in AI. Algorithms are increasingly designing other algorithms, and we often have little meaningful access to track or fully understand how their outputs are produced.

As we move toward more agentic technological futures, this condition will become increasingly present in everyday life. It therefore requires new forms of thinking and learning to emerge. In my work, I believe that behaviour and conversation design theory will play an important role in addressing this challenge.

KH: Architecture has long projected expectations about use and behaviour into spatial form. In responsive systems based on feedback and continuous adjustment, this anticipatory role seems to give way to ongoing modulation. How do you understand this shift, and what does it imply for architecture’s political role today?

TS: This shift has extended into all aspects of life as the communication revolution has transformed both the ways we communicate with each other and the systems that communicate with us. Moving toward an anticipatory model of architecture requires recognising that architecture often remains a form of resistance to these changes. Part of this resistance lies in the implicit time required to realise buildings, but a more significant factor is the habitual way we relate to the built environment; as one of the few legible and consistent artefacts in an otherwise rapidly changing world. However, the conservatism that often shapes our approaches to architecture and urbanism can be dangerous. It risks perpetuating models of development that repeat past mistakes rather than examining meaningful alternatives. Engaging with change, therefore, becomes a necessary and important strategy, one that responds to the accelerated

demands placed on architects and to the volatility of the forces that shape these decisions, whether market-driven, social, or political.

Allowing systems themselves to adapt and evolve could lead to more informed decision-making and create opportunities for more participatory forms of development among diverse stakeholders. Some of the work at the Architectural Association's Design Research Lab (DRL), for example, explores gamified environments that allow people to better understand their surroundings and potentially co-design the spaces they inhabit. Such approaches aim to amplify voices and create learning environments that can influence urban decision-making and design.

An important reference for me in thinking about anticipatory frameworks is Buckminster Fuller's World Game, developed for Expo 67 in response to the exhibition's theme, *Man and His World*. Fuller approached the planet as a unitary system, seeking to make visible the conditions required to "make the world work." His goal was to help humanity design a sustainable future through a conscious exploration of cause and effect, using gameplay to address issues such as energy, poverty, and resource distribution. In doing so, Fuller attempted to bypass what he saw as the limitations of politics and economics constrained by nation-state thinking, which he believed had become an obstacle to solving planetary-scale problems. The ambition of the World Game was to explore how the world might function for 100% of humanity through spontaneous cooperation.

This motivated approach challenged conventional forms of representation. Fuller's efforts included developing a new map projection that minimised territorial distortion, while also constructing one of the earliest interactive interfaces and gamified environments. It was a model that framed a conceptual problem in which design itself played a central role in reimagining how the world might be organised.

KH: When architectural processes are shaped less by discrete decisions than by the calibration of interacting systems, the capacity to act can no longer be grounded in authorship or full foresight. Under these conditions, what distinguishes architecture from engineering, environmental systems, or infrastructural management? Is this distinction a matter of technique, judgement or a particular way of framing problems rather than solving them?

TS: Rather than seeing this as a means to continue treating systemic decisions as products of specialisation, I see it as an opportunity to pursue

a greater synthesis. This tendency can already be seen in emerging sciences that seek broader integration, from genetics and biology to studies of the ecologies in which they operate. To return to some of your earlier questions, it offers a way of seeing the world not as a collection of objects but as a network of relations. This perspective appears in many forms, from the work of physicist Carlo Rovelli to Jack Burnham's writings on kinetic and systems art in the 1970s.

Ultimately, it is a way of framing our understanding of the world. We exist both outside and inside this understanding, acting simultaneously as observers and participants within it.

KH: If adaptive spatial systems shift architecture from a discipline that stabilises knowledge into one that continuously responds to behaviour, feedback and change, how does this transformation affect the production of architectural knowledge itself? Can knowledge still be understood as cumulative, or does it instead emerge as something situational, distributed and contingent?

TS: Intelligence, from my perspective, is not an attribute of a thing. It is relational and demonstrated between things. Knowledge today is ever more important to be understood, and how this will evolve with forms of intelligence that aggregate human knowledge. From my perspective, treating these AIs as conversational partners is an important start, allowing the plasticity of our own knowledge structures to engage in new forms of learning and understanding. A co-intelligent system recognises that what we speak of regarding these systems today is modelled on us and our data. If we recognise that all things have intelligence and leverage these models in a complementary way, we can find the means to address the immediacy of issues, both social, political, and ecological. Only when we shed this notion of explicit control and actively explore meaningful and I will restate, human pursuits that are responsible, will we be able to understand our relationality to the world as necessitating situational and distributed forms of knowledge structures that are context-aware and coherent to the issues that we are facing.

Interview conducted by Andreja Prokopijević, Sara Dragišić, and Snežana Vesnić.

